

DECODING MULTILINGUAL MEANINGS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE USE IN INNER CIRCLE AND INDONESIAN CONTEXTS

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Abstract

This innovative research delves at the complex dynamics of English language usage in both traditional 'Inner Circle' countries (such as the UK, USA, and Australia) and the Indonesian environment. This analysis explores the intricacies of how English words are used and understood in various linguistic contexts, providing an in-depth exploration of the subtle ways in which English adapts to varied cultural and social situations. It is based on several linguistic theories, such as Linguistic Relativity, Multilingualism, Post-Colonialism, Language Dynamics, Sociolinguistics, Cultural Identity, Globalisation, World Englishes, and Pragmatics. Within Inner Circle countries, English serves as more than just a means of communication; it functions as a cultural marker, impacting social stratification and encompassing unique phonetic characteristics and sociolinguistic elements. In contrast, English in Indonesia represents modernity and worldwide interconnectedness, blending with indigenous languages and cultural conventions. This study examines the patterns of adaptation, localization, and standardisation in both contexts, emphasising the influence of globalisation, social media, and digital communication on language usage and evolution. The results demonstrate notable disparities in the utilisation of particular English phrases in each setting, influenced by cultural subtleties and societal conventions. The study highlights the dynamic nature of language, which continuously changes and adjusts in response to cultural, social, and technological changes. It asserts that comprehending the contextual subtleties of language is vital for successful communication in multilingual environments, hence opening avenues for further investigation into linguistic landscapes, the influence of digital communication, and educational ramifications.

Keywords: Linguistic Relativity; Sociolinguistics; Globalisation; Language Adaptation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of linguistic research, the study emerges as a groundbreaking inquiry into the intricacies of language use and perception across different cultural backdrops. At the heart of this research lies the exploration of linguistic assemblage, specifically the comparative analysis of English language usage in traditional 'Inner Circle' countries - primarily English-speaking nations like the UK, USA, and Australia - and the Indonesian-English context. This study is driven by a desire to unravel the complexities of how specific English terms are employed and understood in these contrasting linguistic

environments, offering a rich understanding of the subtle nuances that define English usage across diverse cultural and social settings (Englander, 2014; Fishman, 1982; Sharifian, 2015).

The philosophical underpinnings of this research are manifold, weaving through various strands of linguistic thought. Foremost among these is the concept of Linguistic Relativity and Multilingualism, grounded in the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, which suggests that the structure of a language influences its speakers' worldview or cognition (Hunt & Agnoli, 1991; Lucy, 2015). This study postulates that to truly grasp the multilingual meanings of English, one must decode its varied uses across different cultural and linguistic contexts. Here, the contrasts between 'Inner Circle' English usage and that in Indonesian contexts provide a fertile ground for examination (Fishman, 1982; Woolard, 1992). Another philosophical cornerstone is the perspective of Post-Colonialism and Language Dynamics, particularly pertinent in examining how English, as a language of former colonizers, has been adapted and appropriated in a post-colonial society like Indonesia, forming a stark contrast with its native usage in 'Inner Circle' countries (Joseph, 1996; Lucy, 2015).

Adding depth to these perspectives is the lens of Sociolinguistics and Cultural Identity, viewing language as a social practice intricately linked with cultural identity. This approach becomes instrumental in understanding how Indonesians have woven English into their societal fabric, creating a distinctive English variant that mirrors their cultural identity, as opposed to its traditional usage in native English-speaking countries (Patrão, 2018; Zhifang, 2002). Furthermore, the study takes into account the effects of Globalization and World Englishes, recognizing the transformative impact of globalization on language, and the subsequent emergence of 'World Englishes' in a multilingual country like Indonesia. Lastly, the study also incorporates Pragmatics and Language Use, aiming to understand how context and usage shape language meaning, by analyzing English's practical application in both Inner Circle and Indonesian contexts (Kadarisman, 2015; Pae, 2020).

The backdrop of previous research provides a vital context for this study. Ke & Cahyani (2014) explored the implications of English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) and World Englishes (WE) in English Language Teaching (ELT), challenging the traditional ELT paradigm centered around native-speaker norms. They introduced the concept of ELF as a functional reality in global English use, emphasizing the need for English learners in non-English-speaking countries to pivot their learning targets from native speakers to bilingual or multilingual speakers. Martin-Anatias (2020) investigated the symbolic power of English in contemporary Indonesia, particularly in popular texts following the Reformasi era. This study highlighted English's elevated status and visibility in Indonesian popular narratives, reflecting its entrenched societal role. Tauchid et al. (2022) examined the evolving perception and role of English as an International Language (EIL) among students in non-native English-speaking countries like Indonesia and Japan, underscoring the need for more inclusive and diverse approaches in teaching English.

Despite these insightful contributions, a notable research gap persists. There is a scarcity of comprehensive studies that specifically analyze and compare the use of English in Inner Circle and Indonesian-English contexts. This study aims to bridge this gap by offering an in-depth examination of how specific English words are used and interpreted in these different settings and exploring the cultural, social, and linguistic factors influencing these interpretations. The methodology of this research is designed to be multi-faceted, encompassing both qualitative and comparative analyses, with a focus on gathering and analyzing a diverse range of texts from both Inner Circle and Indonesian-English sources (Zein et al., 2020; Q. Zhang, 2022).

In conclusion, this research not only contributes to the academic discourse on World Englishes and the dynamics of English as a global language but also holds significant implications for the fields of language education, sociolinguistics, and intercultural communication. By analyzing linguistic assemblage in these multilingual contexts, the study aims to enhance our understanding of how languages evolve and adapt in the face of cultural and linguistic contact, providing valuable insights into the complex dynamics of language in our increasingly globalized world (B. B. Kachru, 1990; Pakir, 2010; Sakhiyya, 2019).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Definition and Characteristics of Inner Circle English

Inner Circle English denotes the variant of the English language that is predominantly spoken in nations such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand (Davidson, 2007; R., Mesthrie & Bhatt, 2008). English holds a significant position in these countries, going beyond being the main language (R. Mesthrie, 2008). It is deeply integrated into the social structure, serving as a vital component in education, governance, and daily interactions (Kachru, 1990).

In comparison to the Outer and Expanding Circles, Inner Circle English occupies a distinct and exceptional position (Wakhidah & Adityarini, 2021). The Outer Circle consists of nations such as India, Nigeria, and Singapore, where English, although not the primary language, is crucial for different societal tasks. Conversely, the Expanding Circle include nations such as China, Japan, and Indonesia, where English is primarily acquired and utilised as a second language (Tajeddin & Pakzadian, 2020). Inner Circle English is characterised by its extensive standardisation, particularly in formal settings such as educational materials, official papers, and mainstream media. Nevertheless, this standardisation exists with notable variations in its spoken manifestations (Bruthiaux, 2003; Xiaoqiong & Xianxing, 2011). The English language exhibits a wide range of diversity, as seen in the various accents, dialects, and regional colloquialisms. This diversity encompasses significant variances in pronunciation between American and British English, as well as variations in vocabulary and spelling (Berns, 2005; Nihalani, 2000).

The distinctive phonological features of Inner Circle English, such as the presence of the rhotic accent in American English or the absence of the rhotic nature in British Received Pronunciation, clearly differentiate it from other varieties of English. Although these variations typically adhere to conventional grammatical norms, they also have distinctive features (Ilson, 1985; Low, 2010). For instance, the utilisation of the present perfect tense differs between British and American English. The vocabulary of Inner Circle English is not only extensive but also constantly changing, frequently pioneering the introduction and dissemination of new terminology worldwide.

Sociolinguistic Aspects of Inner Circle English

In countries categorised as belonging to the Inner Circle, English plays a multifaceted role that goes beyond its fundamental purpose as a means of communication (Davydova, 2012; B. Kachru, 2006). It is recognised as a vital component of social identity and a means for cultural representation. In these countries, English not only enables communication but also has a crucial impact on social hierarchy. This phenomenon is well demonstrated by the manner in which specific dialects and accents are associated with either high social status or negative judgement. An exemplary instance is the Received Pronunciation in the UK, sometimes linked to elevated social standing (Britain, 2017; Rezaei et al., 2019; Roach, 2004).

The perceptions of English in these Inner Circle environments are intricate and diverse. English serves as a source of pride and is a fundamental component of both personal and communal identity. Conversely, there is a deliberate endeavour to maintain and safeguard indigenous dialects and languages. This phenomenon is most apparent in countries with several languages, such as Canada and Australia, where there exists a diverse array of linguistic traditions (Nihalani, 2008; X. Zhang & Lütge, 2023). In these circumstances, English's influence is reciprocal - it both influences and is influenced by the indigenous and immigrant languages that are present. This illustration demonstrates the complex and essential role that English language plays in shaping the cultural identities of these varied nations (Alfarhan, 2017; Bruthiaux, 2003).

Importance of Inner Circle English

The importance of the Inner Circle The use of English in the field of international diplomacy serves as evidence of its significant global impact and indispensability (Seidlhofer & Berns, 2009). As the dominant language in important international forums, it plays a crucial role in influencing diplomatic discussions and policies (Truchot, 1994). Within prestigious institutions like the United Nations, NATO, and the World Bank, Inner Circle English is the primary means of communication (Pakir, 2009). The leading position enables effective communication and collaboration across a wide range of countries, simplifying global interactions and decision-making procedures (Kachru, 1990).

Nevertheless, this superiority has both positive and negative consequences. Non-native English-speaking countries face a distinctive problem that may put them at a potential disadvantage (Charles, 2007; Dolgenko et al., 2023). Consequently, the ability to speak English well has become a crucial requirement for actively engaging in these worldwide

discussions (Sarwal, 2019), This fact emphasises the necessity of adopting a well-rounded strategy towards linguistic diversity in global diplomacy, guaranteeing that every perspective is acknowledged and comprehended, irrespective of the individual's mother tongue (Pakir, 2009; Smokotin et al., 2014).

The impact of Inner Circle English on the realm of world politics is evident and extensive. It serves as the common language in important contexts including international summits, negotiations, and treaties (Xiaoqiong & Xianxing, 2011). The extensive utilisation of Inner Circle English greatly influences the formulation and interpretation of international accords, frequently mirroring the linguistic and cultural viewpoints of native English speakers from Inner Circle countries. This phenomenon can influence worldwide policies in a way that could not completely encompass the variety of global viewpoints (Hurn, 2009).

Professionals involved in international affairs, such as diplomats, must possess a high level of expertise in the Inner Circle. English has evolved from being a valuable resource to an indispensable requirement (Xiaoqiong & Xianxing, 2011). The language's importance not only facilitates clear and effective communication, but also offers a cultural and linguistic framework that is crucial for negotiating the complexities of global politics. Many international plans and policies are designed and implemented using this perspective (Lee & Green, 2016).

Inner Circle English plays a significant and complex role in international diplomacy by enabling effective worldwide communication and cooperation. Nevertheless, it also highlights the difficulties of achieving language fairness and the necessity for increased inclusiveness in the global sphere (Lee & Green, 2016). As the field of international relations undergoes constant changes, it is increasingly vital to comprehend and adjust to the linguistic dynamics associated with it (Schnitzer, 1995).

Cultural and Linguistic Dominance of Inner Circle English

The Inner Circle's cultural and linguistic hegemony and the influence of English on worldwide media and entertainment is significant. The impact of Hollywood, together with American and British music, as well as English-language novels and television series, has a profound effect on global markets (Medina & Hurtado, 2018; Xiuhua Shi, 2013). This domination is not solely limited to commercial aspects but also encompasses the assimilation of specific values, lifestyles, and perspectives that frequently mirror those prevalent in Inner Circle communities within non-native English-speaking nations (Hino, 2008; Lee & Green, 2016).

However, this influence is not unilateral. Core group English also experiences adaptation and assimilation into local cultures. In countries such as Japan and South Korea, English phrases are commonly integrated into popular culture (Lee & Green, 2016; Radumilo, 2015). This results in a distinctive cultural amalgamation that encompasses both worldwide impact and regional distinctiveness. These changes demonstrate the flexibility of the English language, as it effortlessly integrates with many cultural practices despite its dominance (Alfarhan, 2017; Xiuhua Shi, 2013; Zeng et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, the dominance of the Inner Circle English presents a substantial risk to the preservation of linguistic diversity, particularly in areas abundant with indigenous languages. As English becomes closely associated with advancement and achievement, indigenous languages face the danger of being underestimated and neglected, resulting in their progressive decrease. The loss incurred is not solely limited to language, but extends to cultural aspects as well, gradually weakening the diverse and valuable fabric of world history (Alfarhan, 2017; Zeng et al., 2023; Q. Zhang, 2022).

As a reaction to this prevailing influence, hybrid languages such as Pidgins and Creoles have arisen. These emerging linguistic structures originate from the fusion of English with indigenous languages, serving as evidence of the ever-evolving nature of language and cultural interchange. Although they symbolise flexibility and durability, they also give rise to intricate inquiries on linguistic integrity and individuality (Shrestha, 2021; Zeng et al., 2023).

The prevailing influence of the Inner Circle English is being increasingly used as the primary language of instruction in the education systems of many nations where English is not the national language. This phenomenon demonstrates the widely recognised need for English in order to remain competitive on a global scale. However, it frequently puts pupils who are not skilled in English at a disadvantage and might weaken the significance and conservation of indigenous languages (Alfarhan, 2017; Dolgenko et al., 2023).

As a result, the dominance of this language is influencing the development of language policies in educational institutions around the world. While giving priority to the English language can provide students with worldwide opportunities, it may also lead to a diminished emphasis on local languages and traditions. The difficulty is to strike a balance, ensuring that kids are prepared for global involvement while also maintaining a strong connection to and respect for their own linguistic and cultural heritage (Venterová, 2018; Xiaohong & Zeegers, 2010).

Overview of Indonesian-English Linguistic Influence

The intricate tapestry of Indonesian-English linguistic influence is a compelling subject, offering a unique window into the interplay of language, culture, and history. The fusion of English with Indonesian language and culture presents a rich field of study, encompassing historical context, distinctive characteristics, societal roles, and the myriad challenges and opportunities that arise from this linguistic melding (Kirkpatrick, 2011; Lowenberg, 1991).

The historical journey of English in Indonesia is intrinsically linked with colonialism and globalization. While Indonesia was not a British colony, the influence of English seeped into the archipelago through global trade, education, and more recently, through the pervasive impact of globalization and the digital revolution. Post-World War II and the subsequent independence era marked a significant shift in Indonesia's linguistic landscape. English gradually emerged as a symbol of modernity and global connectivity, contrasting with its earlier association with colonial domination (Jaya, 2020; Lowenberg, 1991).

Indonesian-English, often characterized as a variety of English influenced by local linguistic and cultural norms, displays distinct features. Phonologically, it carries the imprint of the native Indonesian sound system, leading to unique pronunciations. Lexically, it incorporates English words that have been adapted and given new meanings within the Indonesian context. Grammatically, there are instances where English structure is influenced by the Indonesian language, leading to innovative syntactical constructions. These characteristics not only highlight the linguistic creativity but also reflect the adaptive nature of English as it intersects with Indonesian culture (Saddhono & Sulaksono, 2018).

In contemporary Indonesian society, English serves multiple roles. It is seen as a language of international communication, education, and business, acting as a gateway to global opportunities and advancements. In urban and educated circles, proficiency in English is often associated with social prestige and progressiveness. Moreover, English is increasingly visible in popular media, advertising, and the internet, signaling its growing influence in everyday life. This societal role of English in Indonesia is multifaceted, ranging from a practical tool for global engagement to a marker of social status (Sakhiyya, 2019; Silva, 1970).

The integration of English into the Indonesian linguistic fabric presents both challenges and opportunities. On the one hand, there's the challenge of ensuring that English learning and usage do not overshadow the rich linguistic heritage of Indonesia, which includes hundreds of local languages. There's also the challenge of equitable access to English education, as proficiency often correlates with socioeconomic status (Alrajafi, 2021; Manara, 2019).

On the other hand, the rise of English presents opportunities for Indonesia on the global stage. English as a global lingua franca can open doors for international trade, education, and diplomacy. Moreover, the unique flavor of Indonesian-English can enrich the tapestry of World Englishes, contributing to the global linguistic diversity (Kusumaningputri, 2020; Pakir, 2009).

In essence, the story of Indonesian-English is one of dynamic interaction and adaptation. It's a narrative of how a global language is localized, acquiring new dimensions and roles within a distinct cultural and societal framework. As Indonesia continues to navigate its path in a globalized world, the evolution of Indonesian-English will undoubtedly offer fascinating insights into the ever-changing landscape of language and identity (Adhyawardhani, 2019; Alrajafi, 2021).

Concept of Linguistic Assemblage in Multilingual Societies

Linguistic Assemblage, a fundamental notion in sociolinguistics, pertains to the intricate and interrelated processes by which languages are employed and modified within societies that have many languages. Derived from the notion of 'assemblage' in social theory, it emphasises the intricate, varied, and ever-changing connections within a language system (Hudson, 1996; R. Mesthrie, 2011).

This concept suggests that language usage goes beyond a simple combination of various linguistic factors. Instead, it signifies an intricate network of influences that includes cultural, historical, and social elements. This complexity is most evident in multilingual situations where languages exist together, interact, and frequently merge in diverse ways (Coupland, 2003; Creese & Martin, 2003).

Linguistic Assemblage in multilingual society emphasises that languages are not independent entities, but rather constantly interact and evolve through mutual interaction. This contact facilitates the emergence of novel linguistic forms and practices, demonstrating the fluid and evolving nature of language (MZ, 2019; Pennycook, 2022).

The field of Linguistic Assemblage extensively connects language with culture and society. For instance, the use of the English language in Indonesia not only demonstrates linguistic customs but also signifies Indonesia's historical, cultural, and worldwide affiliations. Having this perspective is essential for comprehending the intricate and diverse characteristics of language within every given civilization (Farxodovna, 2020; Sudirman & Dacholfany, 2020).

Understanding the concept of Linguistic Assemblage is crucial when it comes to language policy and education. It provides direction for developing language policy and educational methods that are more effective and culturally sensitive, recognising the dynamic and changing nature of language following the linguistic characteristics of multilingual populations (Pennycook, 2022; Siyaswati, 2020).

Moreover, in our progressively interconnected world, having a grasp of Linguistic Assemblage is crucial for understanding the process by which languages develop in response to global cultural and economic influences. The paradigm provides a means to examine the interaction between global trends and local language practices, emphasising the interdependence of linguistic advancements on a global scale (Herawati, 2014; Jackson, 2012).

Linguistic Assemblage functions not only as a linguistic notion but also as a tool to understand the interconnectedness of language, culture, and society, especially in the varied and different settings of multilingual societies (Gorter & Cenoz, 2017).

Characteristics

In civilizations with several languages, the occurrence of linguistic assemblage is evident in several fascinating ways, particularly through the blending of languages, the switching between languages, and the addition of multiple layers of language. Each of these traits plays a crucial role in the development and interplay of languages within these varied cultural environments (Arutiunov, 1992; Urban, 2021).

Hybridization in linguistic assemblage refers to the process of combining or fusing distinct languages, resulting in the creation of new dialects or language varieties. This phenomenon is frequently observed in civilizations that have many languages, where different linguistic communities have close interactions (Alawiya et al., 2020; Ginting & Rahman, 2019; Suprayetno et al., 2022). An exemplary instance can be observed in

Indonesia, where English phrases effortlessly assimilate into Bahasa Indonesia, resulting in a distinctive mode of communication. In Inner Circle countries, the convergence of immigrant languages with English facilitates the emergence of pidgins and creoles, each representing a distinct linguistic identity (Ningsih & Luthfiyati, 2020; Syam, 2020).

Code- Switching is a common feature in these societies, where people switch between two or more languages throughout a discussion, often even inside a single sentence. This phenomenon is particularly evident in settings such as Indonesia, where individuals are able to smoothly transition between Bahasa Indonesia, regional dialects, and English. The act of switching is not random; it frequently fulfils particular objectives such as conveying a notion with more accuracy, indicating group affiliation, or accommodating the listener's linguistic inclination (Alawiya et al., 2020; Auer, 1999; Humaera et al., 2018).

Language Layering refers to the existence of many linguistic strata within a language, which are formed as a result of historical, cultural, and social factors. The stratification is apparent in elements like as lexicon, grammar, and phonetics. English has experienced substantial change, assimilating components from Latin, French, Germanic languages, and other sources, resulting in a linguistically intricate tapestry. Indonesian language incorporates indigenous languages, remnants of Dutch from the colonial period, and contemporary influences from English (Alawiya et al., 2020; Alexiadou & Lohndal, 2018; Sugiharto, 2021).

The essential features of linguistic assemblage are crucial for comprehending the evolution and interaction of languages in multilingual environments. The language reflects its dynamic and adaptive nature by continuously altering itself in response to the evolving social and cultural environment (Batubara & Shafira, 2023; Beckner et al., 2009; Bentz et al., 2015; Gil, 2016; Sapir, 2014).

Countries such as India, Switzerland, and Indonesia, which have multilingual societies, showcase a wide range of linguistic diversity.

The presence of several languages in different regions is a result of historical factors including colonisation, migration, and globalisation, leading to distinctive linguistic environments. The idea of Linguistic Assemblage plays a crucial role in structuring the interaction and coexistence of different languages in these civilizations (Khubchandani, 2012; Romaine, 2006).

The presence of several languages in communities enables various linguistic occurrences, such as the fusion of languages, the alternation between languages, and the development of simplified languages and stable languages. This collection of words is not only a linguistic event; it mirrors the historical and cultural stories of a society, as well as its present socio-linguistic patterns (De Swaan, 1993). It exemplifies the process by which languages, under the influence of several causes, undergo development and adjustment within a society.

When we look at Inner Circle countries like the UK, USA, and Australia, we can see that although English usually has a standardised version, it is still influenced by Linguistic

Assemblage. In these areas, the collection of words and phrases is evident through the inclusion of loanwords from many languages. This occurs in communities where English is spoken alongside heritage languages. This process enhances the English language, incorporating additional levels of cultural and linguistic complexity (Pennycook, 2022; Sugiharto, 2021).

An intriguing example of Linguistic Assemblage can be found in Indonesia. In this context, English, despite lacking official status, is extensively employed in domains like as commerce, academia, and mass communication (Siahaan & Mubarak, 2021). The Indonesian encounter with English exemplifies a prominent example of Linguistic Assemblage, in which English blends with local languages, resulting in a distinct English variation. This variety exhibits distinctive syntax, vocabulary, and pronunciation, all of which are shaped by local linguistic features (Endarto, 2020; Maulana, 2020). These examples clearly demonstrate that Linguistic Assemblage has a vital impact on the formation of languages in multilingual cultures. The statement emphasises the dynamic and flexible nature of language, which is shaped by historical, cultural, and social factors.

The comprehension of Linguistic Assemblage requires a fundamental shift in the paradigm of linguistic research. Historically, languages have been analysed independently, assuming a fixed and unchanging characteristic (Beckner et al., 2009; Bentz et al., 2015). Nevertheless, Linguistic Assemblage disputes this viewpoint by highlighting the flexibility and vitality of languages as they blend and develop in multilingual settings. This shift highlights the necessity for linguistic theories to adjust, encompassing phenomena such as hybridization, code-switching, and language layering (Beckner et al., 2009; Ndhlovu, 2015). This will provide a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of language usage in many circumstances, supporting inclusivity.

The reimagining of language learning also carries substantial ramifications for education. Language teaching approaches should adapt to better accommodate the diverse linguistic origins of learners (Heugh, 2018; Porto, 2010). There is an increasing emphasis on the practical and real-world use of language, rather than solely focusing on standardized forms (Bunch, 2013; Heugh, 2018). In addition, educational curriculums are progressively integrating aspects of linguistic diversity, imparting not just the language itself but also the cultural and historical settings that shape language evolution.

The enormous influence of comprehending Linguistic Assemblage is seen in the realm of policy-making. Policy-makers play a crucial role in determining the methods and applications of languages in society (Ndhlovu, 2015; Shi & Langman, 2012). Language policy should be designed to reflect the diverse linguistic landscape of communities, promoting the inclusion of minority languages and dialects (Heugh, 2018). Having this comprehension is essential for formulating policies that improve social integration and promote intercultural understanding, with the aim of reducing language barriers and fostering mutual respect among different language communities (Arifin, 2020; Sudirman & Dacholfany, 2020).

An example of these shifts can be seen in the multilingual schools in Indonesia, where Indonesian, local dialects, and English exist together (Curd-Christiansen & Sun, 2016). Teachers have adopted multilingual strategies to encourage linguistic adaptability, hence fostering a more inclusive educational setting. Similarly, Singapore's "Speak Mandarin Campaign" aims to achieve linguistic equilibrium by incorporating Mandarin alongside other languages such as Malay, Tamil, and English, thus mirroring the nation's rich linguistic diversity (Chiang, 2014; Curdt-Christiansen & Sun, 2016). These activities play a crucial role in fostering social cohesion and enhancing cultural comprehension across diverse language communities.

Current advancements in linguistic study, influenced by the notion of Linguistic Assemblage, encompass investigations into hybrid languages and the application of cutting-edge technology such as AI and machine learning. These technologies play a crucial role in examining intricate linguistic patterns in communities with many languages, emphasising the importance of embracing varied linguistic backgrounds to promote societal harmony (Li et al., 2016; Starr & Hiramoto, 2019).

3. METHODOLOGY

Data Collection Process

This study employed a systematic approach to data collection, aimed at facilitating a comprehensive and comparative analysis of English language usage in Inner Circle countries and Indonesia. The methodology was meticulously designed to capture the intricacies of linguistic expressions and the contextual meanings that emerge in diverse environments (Kachru, 2006; Martin-Anatias, 2020a).

In selecting texts, we adhered to specific criteria that would encompass a broad spectrum of linguistic nuances and cultural contexts. This involved choosing texts across various genres, each demonstrating varying levels of linguistic complexity and relevance to English usage in both Inner Circle and Indonesian settings. To ensure a rounded perspective of language use, our selection included academic works, literary pieces, and media publications (Martin-Anatias, 2018b, 2018a).

The contextual analysis of these texts was pivotal to our study. We delved into the cultural, social, and historical backgrounds of each piece, with a keen focus on idiomatic expressions, colloquial language, and culturally specific references. This comprehensive analysis was crucial in unraveling the deeper meanings and usage of English in different settings (Endarto, 2020; Sudarman et al., 2022).

To guarantee diversity and authenticity in our data, the texts were sourced from a wide array of platforms. These included academic journals, renowned literature, newspapers, and various online media outlets, originating from both the Inner Circle countries and Indonesia. This selection strategy was carefully crafted to mirror the contemporary usage of English in these regions accurately (Jumino et al., 2021; Prasetya, 2021).

The documentation process was executed with precision. Every text was cataloged, noting its source, date of publication, and the context of usage. We maintained digital copies of all texts in a secure database, supported by backup copies, to ensure the integrity and preservation of our data.

This study entails a comprehensive investigation of the usage of the English language, analysing its application in both Inner Circle countries, which are predominantly native English-speaking regions, and in an Indonesian environment (Endarto, 2020; Jaya, 2020). The methodology employs a comprehensive analytical approach, combining comparative and semantic research with cultural interpretation. The inherent connection between language and culture in this particular situation necessitates a qualitative methodology, which provides a more profound and contextually comprehensive comprehension of the material (Englander, 2014; Sabet & Zhang, 2015).

Comparative analysis is a fundamental aspect of our methodology. This entails a methodical examination of the way English is used in various cultural and geographical contexts. I carefully examine a wide range of text sources, including academic papers, media publications, and informal conversations from both Inner Circle countries and Indonesia (Adiantika, 2020; Endarto, 2020). The purpose of this comparison is to elucidate disparities in language structure, usage, and the influence of cultural influences on language expression. We will conduct our study according to predetermined linguistic criteria, encompassing syntax, lexicon, and pragmatics, in order to achieve a comprehensive and structured comparison (Uktolseja et al., 2019).

This work is enhanced by the inclusion of semantic analysis, which is a crucial component. Its primary objective is to analyse the semantics of words, phrases, and sentences within different English settings. This analysis goes beyond the literal interpretations and include the connotative, cultural, and contextual meanings of linguistic expressions. The objective is to have a greater understanding of how meanings are generated and perceived in Inner Circle and Indonesian settings (Syaputri et al., 2021).

Cultural interpretation is a crucial component of our investigation. This element aims to unravel the intricate connection between language and cultural environments. Through the examination of English language usage in both Inner Circle and Indonesian contexts, we will investigate the influence of cultural factors such as beliefs, traditions, and social conventions on language (Kardana et al., 2018; Susilawati, 2020). The study examines variations in politeness methods, idiomatic expressions, and cultural allusions, and analyse the implications of these discrepancies for underlying cultural values. This investigation will heavily rely on cultural anthropology and sociolinguistic theories, offering a framework for comprehending these linguistic occurrences (Sabet & Zhang, 2015).

The use of the qualitative approach in our study is deliberate, as it is known for its efficacy in investigating intricate phenomena such as language and culture. Qualitative research, in contrast to quantitative methodologies, enables a more interpretive examination of language rather than relying on numerical data and statistical analysis (Polkinghorne, 2005; Sabet & Zhang, 2015; Suh et al., 2008). This approach is particularly suitable for

our study, enabling a thorough examination of linguistic nuances, cultural implications, and contextual understandings. Our objective is to collect detailed and descriptive data that captures the intricacies of language use and the intricacies of cultural influence by utilising techniques such as thematic analysis, discourse analysis, and ethnographic investigations (Pelzang & Hutchinson, 2018; Suh et al., 2008).

The technique of my study is designed to offer a thorough investigation of English language usage in different cultural contexts. Through the incorporation of comparative and semantic analysis, along with cultural interpretation, and the utilisation of a qualitative approach, our objective is to decipher the complex interaction between language and culture (Polzenhagen & Wolf, 2010; Vaughan & Jolliffe, 2023). Every methodological element complements the others, guaranteeing a comprehensive comprehension of the subject. The comparative analysis establishes the foundation for comprehending linguistic distinctions, whereas the semantic analysis delves into the underlying meanings and subtleties of language (Mohammed, 2020; Sabet & Zhang, 2015). Cultural interpretation, on the other hand, offers valuable insights into how language is influenced by and mirrors cultural surroundings (Kalisa, 2019). This collaborative method provides a strong framework for a comprehensive examination and comprehension of the complex nature of language usage in both Inner Circle and Indonesian contexts.

4. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study examines the use of language in English-speaking Inner Circle countries and Indonesian contexts, drawing from diverse data sources including as academic papers, media outputs, and conversational transcripts. However diverse the data may be, it is crucial to acknowledge the inherent constraints within its scope. The chosen domains, although indicative, do not comprehensively encompass the complete range of linguistic subtleties prevalent in these countries, particularly in the domains of casual and digital interactions. This constraint emphasises the importance of exercising caution when applying the study's conclusions beyond its specified boundaries.

The analysis of language in this comparative research is primarily focused on the difficulty of subjectivity. Qualitative analysis is inherently vulnerable to the impact of the researcher's linguistic and cultural background. This phenomenon is especially evident in cross-cultural studies, where the understanding of subtle linguistic nuances is intrinsically intricate. Although this research incorporates methods such as peer review and triangulation to reduce bias, the possibility of subjective interpretations remains, which is a notable constraint.

Another crucial factor to take into account is the ever-changing character of language. Language is always changing and adjusting, undergoing evolution and adaptation throughout its existence. This study, while capturing a precise momentary depiction of English language usage, may not comprehensively reflect the continuous transformations, particularly in the swiftly developing domains of digital communication and slang. Hence, the derived findings may have a restricted duration, indicating the necessity for continuous research to keep up with the evolution of language.

Moreover, the presence of cultural prejudice presents a nuanced yet significant obstacle in this comparative investigation. Although there have been deliberate attempts to analyse data without any prejudice, there is still a possibility of unintentional biases when analysing language aspects from other cultures. This element is especially prominent when addressing subtleties and idiomatic expressions, which are firmly entrenched in cultural contexts. Although efforts have been made to reduce this bias, completely eliminating it still poses a difficulty, which is a drawback of the study.

Ultimately, the matter of generalisation comes into play. The findings of this study provide useful insights into the usage of the English language in the specific situations examined. However, it would be inappropriate to generalise these findings to all Inner Circle and Indonesian linguistic environments. The findings of the study are specific to the setting in which they were conducted. Drawing broad conclusions from these findings could result in misunderstandings. Therefore, it is crucial to consider the specific samples and environments that were studied when interpreting the results.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

Word Analysis from Inner Circle English Perspective and from Indonesian-English Perspective

(i) Inner Circle English Perspective:

Based on google here are some English words used in the text recommendation

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=recommendation>

That which is recommended; a suggestion or proposal, now esp. one put forward by an authoritative body.

Meaning from Cambridge Dictionary

a suggestion that something is good or suitable for a particular purpose

Based on the IC context the term signifies 'A suggestion or proposal for a cool place.'

In Inner Circle English, "recommendation" is used to convey the idea of suggesting or proposing a place or activity that is perceived as favorable or enjoyable.

Instagramable

Meaning from Cambridge Dictionary

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/instagrammable#>

In the IC context the word implies 'Attractive or interesting enough to be suitable for photographing and posting on Instagram.'

In Inner Circle English, "Instagramable" has been adopted to describe something visually appealing or interesting, particularly in the context of being suitable for sharing on the social media platform Instagram.

Halal

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=halal>

In the IC context, it means 'Conforming to Islamic dietary laws; specifically, regarding the preparation of meat.'

In Inner Circle English, "halal" is used to convey that the food adheres to Islamic dietary regulations, especially in terms of how the meat is slaughtered and prepared.

Date

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=date>

In IC context, the term implies 'To engage in a social or romantic outing; to determine the time of an event.'

In Inner Circle English, "date" is used to refer to a social activity, often romantic, and also in the context of determining or assigning a specific time to an event or activity.

Gengs

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=geng>

In the IC context, the term is used to refer to 'A group of friends or a close-knit social circle.'

In Inner Circle English, "gengs" is likely adopted as a colloquial term to denote a group of friends or a close social circle.

Bestie

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=bestie>

A person's best friend; a very close friend.

In the IC context, it refers to 'A person's best friend; a very close friend.'

In Inner Circle English, "bestie" is used as an affectionate term for a person's closest and most trusted friend.

(ii) Indonesian-English perspective:

In "Rekomendasi tempat nongkrong asik buat kamu nih!" The writer is suggesting an enjoyable place for the reader to hang out. The use of "Recommendation" is used casually to convey the idea of suggesting a place or activity.

In "Sini sini main ke kafe 2D ini, bikin kamu berasa lagi ada di dunia komik loh!" the intended meaning is inviting the reader to visit a 2D-themed cafe that provides an experience reminiscent of being in a comic world.

In "Tema tiap lantainya beda-beda dan pastinya instagramable banget, jadi gak perlu jauh jauh deh ke luar negeri" the intended Meaning is highlighting the unique themes on each floor of the cafe and emphasizing its Instagrammable qualities, suggesting that there's no need to travel abroad for a similar experience.

"Instagramable" is used seamlessly to describe the visual appeal suitable for sharing on Instagram.

In "Menu menunya unik dan enak -enak loh gaes, harganya mulai dari Rp35.000 dan pastinya halal (no pork no lard)." The intended meaning is describing the cafe's menu as unique and delicious, providing price information, and assuring that the food is halal according to Islamic dietary laws. The word "halal (no pork no lard)" assures compliance with Islamic dietary laws. "Ngedate maupun jalan sama gengs makin seru pastinya, yuk mampir bestie" means that the cafe is suitable for both dates and casual outings with friends, inviting the reader, referred to as "bestie," to visit. "Bestie" is used as an affectionate term for a very close friend, creating a friendly and familiar tone.

The writer is suggesting or proposing a cool place for the reader to hang out. Encouraging the reader to visit a cafe with a 2D theme that creates an experience reminiscent of being in a comic. Highlighting the unique themes on each floor of the cafe, emphasizing its Instagrammable qualities, and suggesting that there's no need to travel abroad for a similar experience. Describing the cafe's menu as distinctive and tasty, providing price information, and assuring that the food is halal according to Islamic dietary laws. Expressing that the cafe is suitable for both dates and casual outings with friends, and inviting the reader, referred to as "bestie," to visit.

[B]

cus Damage yang terakhir efeknya akan bertahun tahun dan masih belum di temukan obatnya.

Note :

Allah tidak meninggalkan kita walau terkadang kita lebih sayang dengan ciptaanNya.

71 w See Translation

Damage yang terakhir efeknya akan bertahun-tahun dan masih belum ditemukan obatnya.

Note: Allah tidak meninggalkan kita walau terkadang kita lebih sayang dengan ciptaanNya.

(i) an Inner Circle English perspective:

Damage

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=damage>

Injury, harm; esp. physical injury to a thing, such as impairs its value or usefulness.

Note

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=note>

A brief written observation, record, or abstract of facts, esp. one intended to aid the memory, or to serve as a basis for a more complete statement.

In "Damage yang terakhir efeknya akan bertahun-tahun dan masih belum ditemukan obatnya." In the Inner Circle English context, "damage" is used to denote harm or injury, especially with long-lasting effects. The phrase emphasizes the enduring impact of the damage and the absence of a known remedy.

In "Note: Allah tidak meninggalkan kita walau terkadang kita lebih sayang dengan ciptaanNya." The word "note" is used to introduce a brief written observation or statement. The message emphasizes the idea that despite human attachment to worldly creations, Allah does not abandon them.

The English words "damage" and "note" are seamlessly integrated into the Indonesian text to convey specific meanings. In both instances, the use of English contributes to a formal and technical tone, adding precision to the expression of ideas. The words maintain their standard Inner Circle English meanings in the context of the Indonesian text, allowing for clear and nuanced communication.

(ii) The meaning as intended by the writer in the text

In this context, "damage" is metaphorically employed to describe the negative consequences or harm resulting from a particular event or situation. The term emphasizes the severity and enduring nature of the difficulties faced. What "Note" does is act as an opening or introduction to a different message. In this situation, it adds a spiritual point of view or thought to the previous sentence. When people face problems or become attached to things in this world, which are called "damage," the note stresses that believers believe that Allah does not leave them. The note stresses how important it is to keep believing in and trusting in Allah, even when things are hard. "Lebih sayang dengan

ciptaanNya" means "more attached to His creation." This means that people may sometimes care more about material things than their spiritual relationship with God.

(i) the meaning as used by the speakers of the Inner Circle

Meaning from Google

Coding

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=coding>

Computing. The conversion of information into code usable by a computer or other machine; the writing or editing of code for a computer program

The word "coding" is used in its computing context, representing the activity of converting information into code for a computer program. In the Inner Circle English context, "coding" is used to refer to the practice of programming or writing code for computer programs.

Timing

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=timing>

To plan, schedule, or arrange the time when (something) should happen or be done, or for how long (something) should go on.

The word "timing" is used in a metaphorical sense, suggesting that the commitment of coding enthusiasts remains steadfast, even when faced with challenges or inconvenient situations.

Ngoding

Meaning from website

<https://infokomputerrakitan.blogspot.com/2019/03/apa-sih-ngoding-itu.html>

Nyekrip atau Ngoding dalam bahasa bakunya adalah "memprogram". Memprogram adalah suatu kegiatan menggunakan bahasa pemrograman dan juga algoritma yang

nantinya akan disusun menjadi satu untuk menciptakan suatu program. Pengertian lainnya adalah “membuat kode dari suatu program. Atau bisa juga diartikan dengan menulis program pada bahasa pemrograman tertentu.

Shopping

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=shopping&tl=true>

The action of visiting a shop or shops to buy or view goods.

The word "shopping" is used to convey a contrast between coding and engaging in the action of visiting shops to buy or view goods. It's used in a playful way to indicate different priorities.

In the Inner Circle English context, the phrase is a playful way of expressing priorities. It suggests that if one is not engaged in coding (programming), then there is no time for or interest in shopping. This phrase could reflect the dedication of individuals to their coding pursuits.

The use of these terms adds humor and a touch of playfulness to convey specific meanings related to priorities and commitment within the coding community.

(ii) the meaning as intended by the writer of the text

The caption, a playful and humorous portrayal of coding enthusiasts, incorporates a humorous take on financial commitment, the focus of a bug hunter, and the dedication to coding over shopping. The writer uses a blend of Indonesian and English to create a relatable message for those involved in the coding world.

(i) the meaning as used by the speakers of the Inner Circle

Data from Google

Circle

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=circle&tl=true>

1. (noun) A perfectly round plane figure. In Geometry defined as a plane figure bounded by a single curved line, called the circumference, which is everywhere...
2. (verb) To make the circuit of, move round.

Referring to social circles or groups with different interests, styles, or backgrounds.

In this context, "circle" is used metaphorically to represent social groups or cliques. The statement suggests that Zizee and Arhan belong to different social circles, possibly indicating contrasting styles or preferences.

Stone island

Meaning from Wikipedia

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stone_Island

Stone Island is an Italian luxury fashion house specialized in men's apparel, outerwear, and accessories headquartered in Ravarino, Emilia-Romagna, Italy. Its core branding includes a Nautical star and compass, both of which is printed or overlaid atop a button-on cloth badge with green, yellow, and black detailing.

The mention of "Stone Island" refers to a specific brand known for its distinctive Nautical star and compass branding. Zizee's choice of clothing from Stone Island is likely seen as a marker of a certain fashion style or status.

"Erigo":

The specific meaning of "Erigo" is not provided in the given information. It might be a brand or reference known within a particular context or community.

The mention of "Erigo" suggests that Arhan has a different fashion preference compared to Zizee, possibly belonging to a different style or brand.

The English words "circle," "Stone Island," and "Erigo" are used to describe social groups and fashion preferences. The expressions reflect the influence of global fashion trends and the use of English terms to convey specific meanings related to style and social circles within the Inner Circle English context.

(ii) the meaning as intended by the writer of the text

The writer is conveying the idea that a romantic or social match might be challenging between Arhan and Zizee because they seem to belong to different social circles, as indicated by their fashion choices:

"Kalo sama Arhan beda circle" suggests that the perceived mismatch stems from Arhan and Zizee being part of distinct social circles or groups with different interests, lifestyles, or preferences.

"Zizee pake Stone Island, Arhan pake Erigo highlights specific fashion brands associated with each individual. Stone Island and Erigo are well-known brands, and the writer uses them to illustrate the perceived difference in fashion preferences between Zizee and Arhan. Arhan and Zizee may not be well-suited romantically or socially due to perceived differences in their social circles and fashion choices, as indicated by the specific brands they wear.

(i) the meaning as used by the speakers of the Inner Circle

Meaning from Cambridge Dictionary

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/booth?q=Booth>

1. (noun) a small space like a box that a person can go into, a partly closed area or small tent at a fair, exhibition, or similar event
2. (noun) an area, table, etc. set up by an organization at a fair or other event to show or sell its products or services:

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=booth>

A covered stall at a market; a tent at a fair, or the like, for the sale or wares or refreshments, exhibition of the feats of jugglers, etc

The term "booth" refers to a specific location, possibly at an event or exhibition where individuals are present to showcase or promote something.

The English words "flirt" and "booth" are used in an Indonesian context to convey a social interaction scenario. The use of these terms adds a colloquial and informal tone to describe engaging with individuals at a booth, possibly in a playful or friendly manner. The expressions reflect the integration of English terms into a localized context to communicate specific social interactions within the Inner Circle English context.

(ii) the meaning as intended by the writer of the text

The writer uses the Indonesian term "Godain" and "mas-mas booth" to express an intention to engage in light flirtation with male individuals working at a specific booth. The term "booth" is implied by the context, likely referring to a booth where people are working, and the writer is expressing a playful interest in engaging with them. The caption suggests an intention to flirt with the guys working at a booth, likely at an event or venue, adding specificity to the playful interaction.

(i) the meaning as used by the speakers of the Inner Circle

Value

Meaning from Cambridge Dictionary

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/value>

The beliefs people have, especially about what is right and wrong and what is most important in life, that control their behaviour

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=value&tl=true>

Transitive. To estimate the value of (goods, property, etc.); to appraise, esp. professionally, in respect of value.

In this context, "values" likely refers to Aden's positive qualities or attributes that make him a valuable or admirable person

Balance

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=balance&tl=true>

To steady (a body under the influence of opposing forces); to poise, keep steady or erect.

Aden can balance well with Karin, suggesting a harmonious and complementary relationship.

Support

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=support>

A thing that holds up, or sustains the weight of, an object, keeps an object upright, or on which an object rests.

Aden has a passion that supports @narinkovilda, indicating a commitment or enthusiasm for a particular interest or cause.

Hobby

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=hobby>

A favourite occupation or topic, pursued merely for the amusement or interest that it affords, and which is compared to the riding of a toy horse

Aden shares the same hobby of traveling, suggesting a common interest or activity that brings enjoyment.

Wise

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=wise>

Manner, mode, fashion, style; spec. habitual manner of action, habit, custom

Inner Circle English Meaning: Possessing good judgment, discernment, or knowledge. Describing Aden as "wise" implies that he has good judgment or makes sensible decisions.

Clingy

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=clingy>

Apt to cling; sticky, adhesive, tenacious

Inner Circle English Meaning: Tending to be overly attached or dependent in a relationship.

Aden seems capable of balancing Karin's clinginess, indicating a skill in managing the dynamics of their relationship.

The expressions describe personal qualities, relationship dynamics, and shared interests. The use of these terms conveys a sense of positivity and compatibility within the Inner Circle English-speaking community.

(ii) the meaning as intended by the writer of the text

The writer praises Aden on Instagram, highlighting his ability to maintain harmony with Karin, his supportive passion, and shared interests in traveling. They also mention Aden's ability to manage Karin's clingy behavior, indicating understanding and compatibility in their relationship. The incomplete sentence expresses high confidence in their relationship's success. The Instagram caption, a mix of Indonesian and English, highlights Aden's ability to handle certain aspects of their relationship, highlighting their shared values and interests. The writer's positive portrayal of Aden on Instagram highlights their compatibility and shared values.

(i) the meaning as used by the speakers of the Inner Circle

Meaning from Oxford English Dictionary

<https://www.oed.com/search/dictionary/?scope=Entries&q=works>

(N) Action or activity involving physical or mental effort and undertaken in order to achieve a result, esp. as a means of making one's living or earning...

Meaning from Cambridge Dictionary

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/works>

Everything that you might want or expect to find in a particular situation

In the Inner Circle English context, "works" is used to convey that the operation or process is successful, efficient, or effective. "operasinya" refers to a specific operation or process, likely within a particular context or field.

The use of "works" in this context reflects a common expression in Inner Circle English to convey that a process or operation is functioning well and achieving the desired outcomes. The sentence suggests a positive assessment of the success or effectiveness of the mentioned operation within the Inner Circle English-speaking community.

(ii) the meaning as intended by the writer of the text

When this writer uses this phrase, they mean that a certain action or process works very well. The phrase "works banget" drives home the good result of the process. The writer likely chose to use the English word "works" for its simplicity and directness, and it is commonly used in Indonesian slang or colloquial language to convey functionality or success. The English word "works" is added to emphasise how well the process works. The caption simply states that the operation is very successful. The writer chose the English word "works" to express a sense of modernity and success concisely.

6. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The comparative analysis of English language usage between Inner Circle countries and Indonesia highlights intriguing similarities and differences, shaped by cultural and social nuances. Key English terms such as "recommendation," "Instagramable," "halal," "date," "gengs," and "bestie" are used in both contexts, yet with distinct variations in meanings and applications.

In Inner Circle English, words like "recommendation," "Instagramable," and "halal" are used in their conventional senses, focusing on suggestions, social media aesthetics, and dietary laws, respectively. "Date" and "gengs" encompass a broader range of social interactions and group dynamics, while "bestie" remains an endearing term for a close friend.

Conversely, in the Indonesian-English context, "recommendation" is casually used to suggest enjoyable places or activities, reflecting a more relaxed and informal tone. "Instagramable" denotes visual appeal on social media, while "halal" assures compliance with Islamic dietary laws, a crucial aspect in Indonesia. "Date" and "gengs" are more specific to social outings, and "bestie" is used to create a friendly and approachable tone.

The cultural backdrop significantly influences the interpretation and usage of these English words. While the basic meanings are retained, cultural nuances in each context shape their application and perception. In Inner Circle English, usage aligns closely with conventional dictionary definitions, focusing on a universal understanding with less pronounced cultural influences. In the Indonesian-English context, however, cultural nuances heavily influence word usage. Terms like "halal" are deeply embedded in religious practices, while informal and casual uses of words like "recommendation" and "bestie" mirror societal norms and conversational styles in Indonesia.

Globalization has had a marked influence on language use in both Inner Circle and Indonesian contexts, driving the permeation of English into various aspects of life. In Inner Circle countries, globalization reinforces English's status as a lingua franca, particularly in professional and academic settings, with a notable incorporation of technical and business jargon. In contrast, in Indonesia, English integration is more evident in everyday conversation, influenced heavily by entertainment and social interactions, and often adapted to fit the phonetic and syntactic patterns of Bahasa Indonesia.

Social media platforms have become hotbeds for linguistic innovation, impacting the use and understanding of English. Both contexts have seen the emergence of internet slang and abbreviated communication. In Inner Circle countries, social media trends often lead to the rapid adoption of new phrases and terminologies. In the Indonesian context, English terms gain popularity on social media and are frequently localized, creating a distinctive blend of Indonesian-English.

The proliferation of memes and the use of hashtags on social media have introduced new words and phrases into the common vernacular. These platforms have influenced language in marketing and casual communication, creating compact and catchy phrases.

In conclusion, while there are similarities in the adoption of English terms and phrases in both contexts, particularly among younger populations and influenced by social media and globalization, notable differences exist. The Inner Circle maintains a more formal and standard use of English, while Indonesian usage exhibits greater flexibility and innovation in adopting and adapting English terms.

7. DISCUSSION

The adaptation and localization patterns found in Indonesian-English provide a strong reflection of the standardisation and evolution of Inner Circle English in the global language landscape. According to researchers like as Bruthiaux (2003) and Xiaoqiong & Xianxing (2011), Inner Circle English, despite being standardised to some extent, is continuously changing by incorporating new expressions and words. The Indonesian method to incorporating English into its indigenous language reflects the flexibility and versatility of language in many cultural and social settings.

An intriguing feature of this language interaction is the noticeable disparity in levels of formality between Inner Circle English and Indonesian-English. The Inner Circle English, which is strongly ingrained in official systems of education and governance as highlighted by Kachru (1990), is distinctly different from the more casual and adaptable nature of Indonesian-English. The disparity between Indonesian-English is primarily influenced by the sociolinguistic landscape, with the structural and societal norms of Bahasa Indonesia playing a crucial role.

Further exploring the topic, the notion of Linguistic Assemblage, as explained by academics such as Coupland (2003) and Creese & Martin (2003), provides a structure for comprehending the intricate dynamics between languages in communities with many languages. The incorporation of English in Indonesia and its increased standardization in

Inner Circle countries exemplify the dynamic process of language evolution and intermingling within unique cultural and societal contexts.

The linguistic developments mentioned have extensive consequences for communication between several languages and the process of globalisation. Theoretical frameworks emphasized by Seidlhofer & Berns (2009) and Xiaoqiong & Xianxing (2011) underscore the worldwide impact of Inner Circle English. The significance of comprehending linguistic subtleties and cultural variety in worldwide contacts, especially in the field of international diplomacy, is emphasised by this linguistic supremacy.

Ultimately, contemplating the prevailing influence of Inner Circle The presence of English in worldwide media and entertainment showcases a multifaceted story of linguistic and cultural interchange. The phenomenon of English adoption in Indonesia, pushed by globalisation, is exemplified by the reciprocal influence between English and local languages, as explored by Alfarhan (2017) and Xiuhua Shi (2013). In this process, both English and local languages mutually influence and are influenced by each other. This interaction demonstrates the complex dynamics of linguistic hegemony and cultural interchange, presenting a world where languages serve not just as means of communication but also as carriers of cultural heritage and global interdependence.

8. CONCLUSION

This study has uncovered significant insights into the utilisation of English in both Inner Circle and Indonesian contexts, providing a sophisticated comprehension of language adaption and usage. An important discovery is the way English terms are adapted, which, although common in both situations, shows a greater level of localization in Indonesia. The process of adaptation is not consistent, but rather varies greatly, influenced by the distinct cultural and contextual factors present in any particular situation.

Cultural backgrounds significantly influence the process of integrating and utilising the English language. Significant disparities exist between the Inner Circle, where English is spoken as a first language, and the Indonesian environment, where it is not. These variations exemplify the numerous manners in which English integrates with indigenous languages and cultural standards, showcasing its exceptional adaptability and ability to develop.

Moreover, the English language has undergone changes due to the emergence of global and social media trends, which have shown to be powerful elements. These tendencies serve as catalysts for the emergence of novel expressions and usage patterns, thereby enhancing the language landscape. This evolution encompasses not only linguistic changes but also cultural transformations, which are a direct result of the always shifting dynamics of global communication. Emphasising the significance of context in interpreting language, the study highlights that language is not fixed or unchanging. The subject is in a perpetual state of change, continuously developing and adjusting to cultural, social, and technical advancements. An essential requirement for successful communication, especially in multilingual settings, is a thorough comprehension of these contextual

subtleties. Language is a reflection of the society it exists in, hence it is important to understand the cultural and social factors that influence its development.

Anticipating the future, the paper proposes various paths for further investigation. Examining the manner in which English adjusts in non-native settings, in contrast to its usage in Inner Circle countries and Indonesia, could yield profound understanding of its worldwide flexibility. Exploring the influence of digital communication platforms on language use and evolution is a promising field of study. Moreover, comprehending the educational ramifications of these observations, especially in the realm of English language instruction in diverse and culturally varied environments, could prove exceedingly advantageous.

Ultimately, this study exemplifies the complex interplay between language and culture. The book highlights the versatility and flexibility of English in many situations, underscoring its continuous development shaped by cultural and global factors. The findings obtained from this study not only enhance our comprehension of the ever-changing characteristics of language but also open up possibilities for more investigation in our progressively interconnected world.

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